

Pathogenicity of *Aspergillus terreus* to the rice grasshopper.

Treatment	Percent mortality due to mycosis ($\bar{X} \pm SD$) ^a
Fungal spore suspension	85.4 \pm 2.9 ^{**b}
Water (control)	17.9 \pm 6.9

^an = 3 replicates, 10 insects per replicate. ^b** Significantly different from control (P<0.01) by LSD test.

pathogenicity of the fungus thus was positive.

The fungus was identified as *Aspergillus terreus* Thom. So far

A. terreus has been known to be a soil fungus of the rice ecosystem and this is the first time it has been observed as an insect pathogen. The presence of the spores in the air of the rice ecosystem made it possible for the fungus to infect the rice grasshopper.

Fungus incidence peaked during the first half of Feb 1996 at Annamalai-nagar, which coincided with the maximum field population of the grasshopper (8-10 nymphs or adults net sweep⁻¹). Nearly 6-8 diseased grasshoppers were detected on the leaf

lamina of rice plants at four locations randomly selected in the field. Climatic factors, such as 95% relative humidity and temperatures of 30 °C (max) and 24 °C (min), may have promoted the fungal infection.

Because of its field adaptability and high infectivity, *A. terreus* appears to be a potential candidate for developing a "mycoinsecticide" to biologically control grasshoppers in the future.

The CAB International Mycological Institute in London identified the fungus. ■

Integrated pest management — weeds

Weed control practices for improving N use efficiency and productivity of flood-prone lowland rice

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Flood-prone lowland rice in eastern India is mostly dry-sown through broadcasting seeds on poorly prepared fields, a practice resulting in early weed infestation and inefficient use of basally applied fertilizers. Nitrogen use efficiency can be improved by controlling weeds through off-season tillage operations and adopting mechanical or chemical methods in the early stages.

We investigated the effects of tillage, weed control practices, and N fertilizer on the performance of rice during 1994 at Cuttack, India. A split-plot design,

Daily variations in flooding patterns in the field during the growing period of rice. Arrows indicate dates of sowing (s), germination (g), beushani/transplanting (t), and harvesting (h) of rice. Cuttack, India.

with tillage in main plots and combinations of weed control and N fertilizer in subplots, was used in three replications. The crop was grown in plots plowed in summer (Mar) and/or before sowing (late May) or transplanting (late July) (conventional tillage) with or without basal application of 40 kg N ha⁻¹. The crop was sown in dry soil on 1 Jun using 400 seeds m⁻² at 20-cm row spacing, and sprayed with thiobencarb at 2 kg ha⁻¹ within a week of sowing or subjected to beushani at 42 d after water accumulated in the field. Puddling was also included as an additional treatment for comparison, where 42-d-old seedlings were transplanted at 20- × 15-cm spacing using 3-4 seedlings hill⁻¹. Gayatri, a semidwarf, long-duration, photoperiod-sensitive rice variety, was used in the experiment.

Seeds germinated with the monsoon showers. Water started accumulating in the field from mid-July onward following regular monsoon showers (see figure). Water depth fluctuated widely, rising from 0 cm at 22 d after germination (DAG) to 54 cm at 36 DAG and receding to 0 cm at 52 DAG. The crops subjected to beushani or transplanted at 42 DAG at 12 cm water depth established well because the water level remained <10 cm up to 20 d thereafter. Peak flooding of 60 cm occurred in the late vegetative growth stages (78-84 DAG) and the crop

experienced extreme excess water stress for 10 d. Water level showed a declining trend from September and had receded completely by late October.

Yield performance of rice was poor because of inadequate crop stand. Excessive flooding at both early and late vegetative stages resulted in restricted tiller production and greater mortality, leading to only 50-70 panicles m⁻² at maturity (Table 1). The mean grain yield was significantly more with summer plowing than with conventional tillage because of the beneficial effect on the number and weight of panicles. Weed control efficiency from summer plowing was 56.3% compared with conventional tillage. The rice plants remained short and produced fewer panicles m⁻² in the unweeded control than when weeds were controlled. Controlling weeds by chemical or mechanical methods improved grain yield significantly. The grain yield was highest with puddling, a practice that was on a par with the direct-sown crop under beushani but significantly higher than chemical weeding. Increase in yield was associated with a decrease in weed dry weight, which was lowest with puddling. The transplanted crop remained virtually weed-free throughout because growing weeds were incorporated thoroughly during puddling, and subsequent higher

Table 1. Mean effect of tillage, weed control practice, and N level on performance of rice and dry weight of weeds at harvest. Cuttack, India.

Treatment	Plant height at maturity (cm)	Panicles m ⁻² (no.)	Panicle weight (g)	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Straw yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Weed dry weight (g m ⁻²)
Tillage						
Summer plowing	115	67	2.79	2.78	3.12	67
Conventional tillage	116	58	2.57	1.98	2.86	142
SE	1.2	2.4	0.049	0.055	0.085	3.9
Weed control practice						
No weeding	113	52	2.47	1.73	2.33	235
Chemical weeding	120	64	2.74	2.33	3.03	105
Beushani	114	62	2.73	2.68	3.14	43
Puddling	115	72	2.78	2.77	3.48	35
SE	1.3	2.5	0.046	0.062	0.095	3.5
N level (kg ha⁻¹)						
0	110	55	2.56	2.12	2.41	93
40	121	70	2.81	2.63	3.58	116
SE	0.9	1.8	0.033	0.044	0.067	2.4

Table 2. Interaction between tillage, weed control practice, and N level and effect on grain yield of rice (t ha⁻¹). Cuttack, India.

Treatment	Weed control practice				Mean
	No weeding	Chemical weeding	Beushani	Puddling	
Tillage					
Summer plowing	2.11	2.86	3.02	3.13	2.78
Conventional tillage	1.35	1.80	2.34	2.42	1.98
N level (kg ha⁻¹)					
0	1.55	2.02	2.43	2.50	2.12
40	1.91	2.64	2.94	3.05	2.63
Mean	1.73	2.33	2.68	2.77	
SE					
Tillage	0.055				
Weed control practice	0.062				
N level	0.044				
Tillage × weed control	0.126				
Weed control × N level	0.126				

water depth and fast canopy closure did not allow the weeds to come up. Thiobencarb did not effectively control broadleaf weeds (mainly jointvetch) and late emerging aquatic weeds. Applying 40 kg N ha⁻¹ increased plant height and number and weight of panicles and led to significantly larger grain yields, despite increased weed biomass.

Interactions between weed control practices and tillage or N levels were significant for grain yield of rice (Table 2). Inadequate land preparation under conventional tillage resulted in profuse weed growth from the early stages, which greatly reduced yield in the unweeded control and chemical weeding treatment. The differences in yield between summer plowing and conventional tillage, however, narrowed under beushani and puddling because of a considerable increase in weed biomass. Basal fertilization with N encouraged weed growth in the early stages, suppressed the growth of rice plants, and thus did not benefit the crop under the unweeded control. The increase in yield from N was significant, however, when weeds were controlled by either cultural or chemical methods. ■

Water management

On-farm water management studies in ricefields of north Bihar, India

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We studied the effects of applying improved water management technology during the wet season in canal-irrigated ricefields for 6 yr (1989-94) in the Jian minor canal of the Tirhut main canal in Gandak command, Bihar,

India. We irrigated rice to a depth of 7 cm 3 d after ponded water disappeared. This treatment was compared with the usual farmers' practice of irrigating according to the availability of water from canals and rain. Farmers generally apply more than 10 cm irrigation water continuously, especially in the head of the minor canal. Six to 18 farms were used in the study each year, with an average field size of 0.4 ha (see table). Soil was silty loam. A stage level recorder at the opening of the minor canal and Parshall flume in each outlet were used to measure irrigation water used.

In the study fields (improved practices), semitall improved rice variety Rajshree with maturity period of 145 d was tested against local photoperiod-sensitive tall aman cv Bakol (maturity 165 d) in the control (traditional practices) fields. Irrigation water varied across years depending on the amount of rain. The water use efficiency (WUE) was expressed as the ratio of grain yield to the amount of irrigation water applied. The yield and WUE of the control and study fields were statistically analyzed in a randomized block design, using number of observations as replications.